

2 Supplementary Material

3

4 Appendix 1 – Microclimate logger data details

5 *Site selection*

6 Initially, we aimed at establishing several site pairs (attacked, healthy) that share similar site qualities
7 regarding forest type and topography. In order to do so, we split up each reserve in 50x50 m raster
8 cells and assigned each cell to a synthetic group that described four features relevant to microclimate:
9 soil moisture, elevation, solar radiation and volume of spruce. We used maps of each of these features
10 and classified them into low, medium and high values. Additionally, we had shape polygons available
11 delineating recent bark beetle attacks identified during inventories in 2019 (provided by
12 Södermanland County Administrative Board). In the field, we tried to establish site pairs that belong
13 to the same synthetic group (i.e., that had similar soil moisture, elevation, solar radiation and volume
14 of spruce) within a given nature reserve. In Fig. S1, this would correspond to cells of the same color
15 code. However, the final site selection for the microclimate loggers in the field had to be adjusted to
16 the facts that a) attacks had progressed into new areas, and b) forest stands were rarely completely
17 dead or completely healthy but rather a mix of dead and healthy trees. Therefore, we ended up with
18 about half of the sites classified as completely healthy during site selection in summer 2021, and the
19 rest of the sites having various degrees of attack severity.

20

21 *Fig. S1. Example map of Ekeby reserve. Each 50x50m cell is assigned a group/color that has a four-digit*
22 *code consisting of four combined properties of that cell (in that order: proportion spruce, elevation,*
23 *topographic heat load, soil moisture). 1 = low, 2 = medium, 3 = high. Yellow polygons were reported*

24 attacks from inventories in 2019 and 2020 provided by the County Board Administration
25 (Länsstyrelsen) Södermanland.

26

27 *Fig. S2. Microclimate loggers at one of the 31 forest sites. We used data from one of the two loggers,*
28 *which was attached to the north side of a tree under a white radiation and rain shield, measuring air*
29 *temperature at 2.0 m height.*

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Site ID	Nature Reserve	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation [m]	Basal area (m ³ /ha)						Prop. Dead spruce	Prop. Deciduous	Canopy openness [%]	
					Dead spruce	Spruce	Pine	Larch	Birch	Alder				Aspen
1	Ekeby	59.0179	17.2757	76	24.0	2.0	2.5		1.0			81.36	3.39	13.1
2	Ekeby	59.0170	17.2761	84	23.0	0.5	8.5		0.5			70.77	1.54	11.9
3	Ekeby	59.0166	17.2810	69	35.0	0.5	0.5		0.0	0.5		95.89	1.37	13.7
4	Ekeby	59.0151	17.2812	75	0.0	18.0	1.5		0.0			0.00	0.00	13.6
5	Ekeby	59.0099	17.2814	71	33.0	1.5	0.5		1.0		2.5	85.71	9.09	13.4
6	Ekeby	59.0098	17.2835	71	20.5	0.0	3.0		0.5			85.42	2.08	22.7
7	Ekeby	59.0103	17.2869	76	0.0	14.0	13.0		1.5			0.00	5.26	9.2
8	Ekeby	59.0097	17.2885	72	5.0	19.5	9.5		2.5			13.70	6.85	6.6
9	Ekeby	59.0130	17.2817	83	0.0	11.0	5.0		7.0			0.00	30.43	10.1
10	ToreGrav	58.9414	17.1655	86	13.5	0.0	7.5	1.0	9.0			43.55	29.03	15.8
11	ToreGrav	58.9398	17.1656	84	10.0	1.5	9.0		0.5			47.62	2.38	12.5
12	ToreGrav	58.9409	17.1656	88	17.0	1.5	5.0	4.5	5.0			51.52	15.15	15.7
13	Frakenka rret	58.9349	17.1951	77	0.0	29.5	0.0		0.0			0.00	0.00	11.0
14	Frakenka rret	58.9308	17.1929	56	21.0	0.0	3.0		0.0	0.0	0.0	87.50	0.00	29.5
15	Frakenka rret	58.9319	17.1934	59	21.0	0.0	8.0		0.0	0.0	0.0	72.41	0.00	22.8
16	Frakenka rret	58.9274	17.1889	68	0.0	4.5	21.0		3.5	0.0	0.0	0.00	12.07	14.6
17	Frakenka rret	58.9281	17.1839	64	36.5	0.0	2.5		0.0	0.0	0.0	93.59	0.00	18.6
18	Frakenka rret	58.9291	17.1858	50	0.0	6.0	20.5		7.5	0.0	0.0	0.00	22.06	11.0
19	Frakenka rret	58.9328	17.2022	58	21.0	0.0	3.0		0.5			85.71	2.04	30.7
20	Frakenka rret	58.9168	17.1978	65	12.0	3.5	6.0		4.0	0.0	0.0	47.06	15.69	11.3
21H	Frakenka rret	58.9161	17.2010	66	23.5	6.0	0.0		0.5	0.0	4.0	69.12	13.24	14.5
21B	Storhulte ts	58.8336	17.0435	45	23.5	0.0	10.5		0.0	0.0	0.0	69.12	0.00	17.1
22	Storhulte ts	58.8345	17.0429	48	16.0	1.0	15.0		0.0	0.0	0.0	50.00	0.00	9.7
23	Storhulte ts	58.8362	17.0441	58	19.5	1.0	7.5		0.0	0.0	0.0	69.64	0.00	18.9
24	Storhulte ts	58.8372	17.0432	51	0.0	23.0	1.0		3.5	0.0	0.0	0.00	12.73	7.4
25	Storhulte ts	58.8374	17.0476	60	2.0	19.5	10.5		0.0	0.0	0.0	6.25	0.00	8.9
26	Storhulte ts	58.8331	17.0455	64	12.5	2.5	17.0		1.5	0.0	0.0	37.31	4.48	11.7
27	Noresjon	58.8956	17.4123	54	20.5	2.5	9.0		1.0	0.0	0.0	62.12	3.03	18.3
28	Noresjon	58.8965	17.4116	52	0.0	14.5	12.0		1.0	2.0	0.0	0.00	10.17	7.8
29	Noresjon	58.8982	17.4087	75	20.0	0.0	5.0		0.5	0.0	0.0	78.43	1.96	19.8
30	Noresjon	58.8981	17.4072	60	1.0	23.0	2.0		3.0	0.0	0.0	3.45	10.34	6.9

32 *Table S1. Site characteristics for the 31 logger sites.*

34

35 *Fig. S3. Pearson correlation matrix of daily logger temperature data, daily weather data and site*
 36 *properties. gap_fraction = canopy openness estimates from hemispherical images (%). prop_decid =*
 37 *proportion of deciduous trees from basal area measurements. clouds = cloud cover (%).*

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41 Appendix 2 – Tree top identification and classification details

42 This study used the framework developed in previous studies to detect trees and classify healthy and
43 dead trees from drone images (Huo et al. 2023). The images were first smoothed using a Gaussian
44 smoothing filter on the green-band raster and the points with local maximum pixel values were
45 detected. Those points contained treetops with the brightest pixels and points from the ground. We
46 obtained the heights of those points from CHM generated by the dense cloud from drone images, and
47 only used points with height > 10 m as tree tops. The reflectances in the green, red, and blue bands
48 from those tree tops were obtained, and the Green Leaf Index (GLI) was calculated using Eq. (1), which
49 has been shown sufficient to classify healthy and dead trees (Huo et al. 2023; Eng et al. 2019). The
50 points from healthy and dead trees were classified using k-means clustering on GLI values, which is an
51 unsupervised classification method (Seber 1984). The framework and parameters were commonly
52 used to detect dead trees in drone images (Näsi et al. 2018; Näsi et al. 2015; Minařík et al. 2020;
53 Georgiev et al. 2022). The detection results were then visually examined. Points not from tree tops
54 were removed and points wrongly classified were corrected.

$$55 \quad GLI = \frac{2Green-Red-Blue}{2Green+Red+Blue} \quad \text{Eq.(1)}$$

56

57 (a)

(b)

58 *Fig. S4. Examples of tree detection (a) and classification of healthy (yellow points, b) and dead trees*
59 *(red points, b).*

60

61 References

62 Eng, Lim Soon; Ismail, Rozita; Hashim, Wahidah; Baharum, Aslina (2019): The Use of VARI, GLI, and
63 VIgreen Formulas in Detecting Vegetation In aerial Images. In *IJTech* 10 (7), p. 1385. DOI:
64 10.14716/ijtech.v10i7.3275.

65 Georgiev, Georgi; Georgieva, Margarita; Dimitrov, Stelian; Iliev, Martin; Trenkin, Vladislav; Mirchev,
66 Plamen; Belilov, Sevdalin (2022): Remote Sensing Assessment of the Expansion of *Ips typographus*
67 Attacks in the Chuprene Reserve, Western Balkan Range. In *Forests* 13 (1), p. 39. DOI:
68 10.3390/f13010039.

69 Huo, Langning; Lindberg, Eva; Bohlin, Jonas; Persson, Henrik Jan (2023): Assessing the detectability of
70 European spruce bark beetle green attack in multispectral drone images with high spatial- and
71 temporal resolutions. In *Remote Sensing of Environment* 287 (2), p. 113484. DOI:
72 10.1016/j.rse.2023.113484.

73 Huo, Langning; Persson, Henrik Jan; Bohlin, Jonas; Lindberg, Eva: Green Attack or Overfitting?
74 Comparing Machine-Learning- and Vegetation-Index-Based Methods to Early Detect European Spruce
75 Bark Beetle Attacks Using Multispectral Drone Images. In : IGARSS 2023 The International Geoscience
76 and Remote Sensing Symposium, pp. 546–549.

77 Minařík, Robert; Langhammer, Jakub; Lendzioch, Theodora (2020): Automatic Tree Crown Extraction
78 from UAS Multispectral Imagery for the Detection of Bark Beetle Disturbance in Mixed Forests. In
79 *Remote Sensing* 12 (24), p. 4081. DOI: 10.3390/rs12244081.

80 Näsi, Roope; Honkavaara, Eija; Blomqvist, Minna; Lyytikäinen-Saarenmaa, Päivi; Hakala, Teemu;
81 Viljanen, Niko et al. (2018): Remote sensing of bark beetle damage in urban forests at individual tree
82 level using a novel hyperspectral camera from UAV and aircraft. In *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*
83 30 (4), pp. 72–83. DOI: 10.1016/j.ufug.2018.01.010.

84 Näsi, Roope; Honkavaara, Eija; Lyytikäinen-Saarenmaa, Päivi; Blomqvist, Minna; Litkey, Paula; Hakala,
85 Teemu et al. (2015): Using UAV-Based Photogrammetry and Hyperspectral Imaging for Mapping Bark
86 Beetle Damage at Tree-Level. In *Remote Sensing* 7 (11), pp. 15467–15493. DOI: 10.3390/rs71115467.

87 Seber, G. A. F. (1984): *Multivariate Observations*. With assistance of Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons,
88 Inc.

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94 Appendix 3 – Alternative models with canopy openness instead of attack severity

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96 *Table S2. Results of the multiple linear regressions on summer average maximum or minimum*
 97 *understory temperature (measured by loggers installed at 2 m height) as a function of bark beetle*
 98 *attack severity (prop dead spruce) or canopy openness (gap fraction). Both variables were highly*
 99 *correlated, which is why they were not used together in the same model.*

<i>Predictors</i>	tmax_summer			tmax_summer			tmin_summer			tmin_summer		
	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	21.52	20.55 – 22.49	<0.001	19.90	18.56 – 21.24	<0.001	11.85	10.59 – 13.10	<0.001	12.69	11.05 – 14.33	<0.001
prop dead spruce	0.02	0.01 – 0.02	<0.001				-0.01	-0.01 – 0.00	0.104			
prop decid	0.03	0.00 – 0.06	0.036	0.05	-0.03 – 0.13	0.194	0.00	-0.03 – 0.04	0.794	-0.06	-0.16 – 0.03	0.181
basal area	-0.02	-0.05 – 0.01	0.220	0.02	-0.02 – 0.05	0.338	0.02	-0.02 – 0.06	0.358	-0.00	-0.04 – 0.04	0.943
prop dead spruce × prop decid	-0.00	-0.00 – -0.00	0.001				0.00	-0.00 – 0.00	0.573			
gap fraction				0.09	0.05 – 0.12	<0.001				-0.04	-0.08 – 0.01	0.095
gap fraction × prop decid				-0.00	-0.01 – 0.00	0.137				0.01	-0.00 – 0.01	0.088
Observations	31			31			31			31		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.622 / 0.564			0.594 / 0.532			0.199 / 0.075			0.221 / 0.101		

100

101 Appendix 4 – Canopy temperature estimates based on other emissivity corrections

102
 103 *Fig. S5. Difference in individual tree canopy temperature of living and dead trees in the Ekeby nature*
 104 *reserve during two summer days, one cloudy day (upper panel, n = 8845) and one sunny day (lower*
 105 *panel, n = 9687). Canopy temperatures were derived from UAV-derived thermal images applying three*
 106 *different methods to correct for thermal emissivity (NDVI threshold, Fixed 0.98 and Fixed 0.90).*
 107 *Differences between the categories “dead” and “alive” were significant in all cases (p < .0001, two-*
 108 *sided Welch test, see Table S3). Icons from Flaticon.com.*

109
 110 *Table S3. Results of two-sided Welch tests testing the temperature difference of living (“alive”) and*
 111 *“dead” trees derived from two UAV-flight missions during a sunny and a cloudy day and correcting the*
 112 *thermal images for emissivity using three different approaches.*

Day	Emissivity	t	df	p	T alive [°C]	T dead [°C]
sunny	NDVI	-67.338	3503.9	< 0.001	18.13436	20.74591
sunny	Fixed 0.98	-37.55	3557.5	< 0.001	17.82745	19.14553
sunny	Fixed 0.90	-37.784	3566.7	< 0.001	19.55671	20.96442
cloudy	NDVI	-33.5	3903.3	< 0.001	15.90745	16.60331
cloudy	Fixed 0.98	-38.105	4081.3	< 0.001	15.92906	16.67117
cloudy	Fixed 0.90	-38.121	4083.6	< 0.001	15.78536	16.59421

113

114 **Appendix 5 - Weather conditions during UAV flights**

115

116 # Ekeby on 2021-07-31 "cloudy day"

117

118 First image: 31/07/2021 07:32 UTC

119 Last image: 31/07/2021 09:06 UTC

120 Temperatur: 19°C

121 Relative humidity: 63%

122

123	Date	Time	Temp (0°C)	RH (%)	Wind (m/s)	Cloud cover (%)
124	2021-07-31	07:00:00	18.7	66	3.7	100
125	2021-07-31	08:00:00	19	62	3.5	100
126	2021-07-31	09:00:00	19	63	3	100

127

128 # Ekeby on 2021-07-21 "clear day"

129

130 Ekeby 1:

131 First image: 21/07/2021 09:38 UTC

132 Last image: 21/07/2021 09:58 UTC

133 Temperatur: 20.5°C

134 Relative humidity: 34%

135

136 Ekeby 2:

137 First image: 21/07/2021 10:46 UTC

138 Last image: 21/07/2021 11:02 UTC

139 Temperatur: 21.8°C

140 Relative humidity: 35%

141

142	Date	Time	Temp (0°C)	RH(%)	Wind (m/s)	Cloud cover (%)
143	2021-07-21	09:00:00	19.3	38	1.9	0
144	2021-07-21	10:00:00	20.9	33	2.6	0
145	2021-07-21	11:00:00	22	36	2	0

146